

A STUDY ON DeFi BASED CRYPTO CURRENCY

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ABSTRACT

Over the past year, the sub-sector of DeFi (decentralized finance) within the burgeoning field of crypto currencies has grown rapidly, and with it, so has its significance for the entire space of crypto currencies. From straightforward peer-to-peer transactions to intricate uses like lending and exchanges, currencies have evolved. DeFi is a cutting-edge disruptive procedure that encourages the development and issuance of a wide range of financial services and products using blockchain technology. These services are implemented as a suite of smart contracts, or software programs that encode the logic of traditional financial operations, via a variety of DeFi protocols. To keep control over their money, DeFi users interact with software programs that combine the resources of other DeFi users rather than transacting with counterparties. In this research study we will explore Ethereum and decentralized finance and characteristics of DeFi. The study will also focus on impact of DeFi in crypto market. The study has also highlighted advantages and disadvantages investing in DeFi crypto currency tokens/coins.

Keywords: Crypto Currency, DeFi, Smart Contracts, Blockchain, Financial Activities.

INTRODUCTION :

Decentralized Finance is known as DeFi. It comprises a wide range of financial activities that are operating on distributed ledgers or the famous blockchain technology. DeFi includes of trading, borrowing, lending, and also investing. We can say it is a digital version of the old traditional banks and financial services that was used by an individual. DeFi utilizes the power of the famous blockchain and primarily Ethereum technology of this era. Similar to how online e-commerce platforms reduce the need for middlemen to streamline transactions, DeFi provides a comparable solution for financial services. It reinterprets the traditional banking model and offers a blockchain-based substitute that charges a small service fee. These services are also available 24/7, facilitating international transactions without the need for middlemen or disclosing personal identity information.

Although centralized financial systems function within regulatory frameworks, decentralized financial infrastructure poses a challenge. As a result, depending on its jurisdiction, many aspects of DeFi are outside the purview of current regulations. The legal status of DeFi systems is determined by various jurisdictions worldwide. DeFi functions lawfully within the defined bounds in nations with explicit guidelines. In order to protect consumers, stop money laundering, and guard against other financial risks, they are subject to particular licensing requirements and must abide by laws and regulations. DeFi was added to the FATF's guidelines for cryptocurrency service providers in October 2021, indicating the body's intention to regulate this kind of asset. They anticipate that each nation will decide whether or not its citizens who engage in DeFi qualify as virtual asset providers and are therefore governed by the guidelines set forth by the FATF.

LITERATURE REVIEW :

Baur et al[2018], according to the authors of the study, the term "decentralized finance" is very broad because, by definition, the majority of blockchain projects are decentralized, and any crypto currency, such as Bitcoin, can be classified as a financial asset. The majority of the literature views DeFi as the blockchain equivalent of financial services complete with all of its subtleties. The writers offer a more accurate classification of the offerings.

Liu et al [2020], the writers concentrate on particular interoperability services, such as oracles. Unquestionably, from USD 1 billion in June 2020 to USD 2 billion in July 2020 to USD 4 billion in August 2020, the sum of money confined in DeFi smart contracts is increasing exponentially. The market capitalization of the tradable tokens underlying the DeFi projects has exceeded USD 10 billion. To put it another way, the authors clarify that the market value of companies involved in decentralized finance is rising along with the utilization of these new services.

Thomas Leirvik [2021], in his paper, the author has demonstrated an upward correlation between liquidity volatility and expected returns.

The relationship between the market capitalization returns of the top five cryptocurrencies and the unusual volatility of market liquidity was investigated by the author. He found that returns and liquidity volatility have a robust overall positive correlation, albeit one that fluctuates significantly over time. This implies that investors are willing to pay more when liquidity volatility is high. He also found that returns and liquidity generally have a positive correlation, which means that when funding is low, expected returns are high. The results corroborate findings from various other financial markets.

Mieszko Mazur [2021], in this study, the author looks at the risks and rewards associated with NFT-based emerging companies listed on cryptocurrency exchanges. The author investigates the cause of the recent upsurge in NFT activity from producers, traders, and investors. He begins by providing a distinct categorization of the existing NFTs, encompassing NFT blockchains, NFT metaverse, and NFT DeFi. After completing a final examination of the research paper, he comes to the conclusion that the inclusion of NFT infrastructure raises the market values of the existing blockchains.

Fadel Dabaja and Tobias Dahlberg [2021], the price of ether, the main currency in DeFi, native token prices on related platforms, and total value locked (TVL) in DeFi were all investigated by the authors.

Lennart Ante [2022], the author's study investigated the relationships among NFT sales, NFT users (private, active blockchain wallets), and the market prices of BTC and ETH. Using daily data from January 2018 to April 2021, he shows that a shock to the price of Bitcoin causes an increase in NFT sales. The number of NFT wallets in use is also decreased by price fluctuations in ether. The results suggest that the growth and progress of the (smaller) NFT market and the (larger) crypto currency markets do not have a negative relationship.

OBJECTIVES :

- To explore the impact of DeFi on market.
- Characteristic features of DeFi.
- To explore the Ethereum and decentralized finance.
- Advantages and disadvantages investing in DeFi crypto currency tokens/coins.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY :

Widely used qualitative and quantitative methodologies were used for this study investigation. For this study primary data was used, survey questions was specially created for data collection and were used. Ten questions based on DeFi crypto currency tokens or coins and questions related to crypto wallets were given to the participants in this research study. The respondents had enough time to read the questionnaire, understand it, and ask any questions they might have had about the study or the questionnaire before completing it. The 100 respondents who were chosen for the study represented all possible lifestyles from region India. The response rate for the entire study was 100%.

IMPACT OF DEFI ON MARKET :

Although making up only 5,6% of the entire cryptocurrency market, the DeFi sub-sector has grown dramatically since DeFi Summer. The three main lending platforms are Aave, Compound, and MakerDAO. Individuals can stake liquidity on these platforms, allowing other users to borrow from them at a predetermined interest rate and with collateral provided.

There is no middleman in DeFi because users communicate directly through the smart contracts on the platform, in contrast to how lending operates in traditional finance, where financial institutions act as the reliable intermediaries that coordinate between lenders and borrowers. The distinct role that banks play in creating money is another area of difference. They are able to make loans greater than what they have on hand by using the fractional reserve system. This article does not address the problems that arise from such a system, but it is important to note that there is a risk of bank runs during hard times. The banks would soon run out of the reserves used to finance their loans, which would result in defaults, if a sudden wave of depositors withdrew their money. In 2008, a similar dynamic led to bank defaults as the collapse of the housing market nearly rendered the holdings of financial institutions worthless. On the other hand, the average over-collateralization on DeFi platforms is 258%, which means that a borrower typically needs to provide \$258 in collateral in order to borrow \$100. Though there is significant asset price volatility, the resulting system is theoretically more reliable than fractional reserve banking because borrower the excess collateral predominates rather than lender leverage.

Decentralized exchanges, of which Uniswap, Curve Finance, Sushiswap, and Balancer are the main players, make up a significant portion of DeFi. DEXes are open, decentralized peer-to-peer applications that run on distributed ledger technology (DLT), which makes them fundamentally different from centralized exchanges in that users can trade digital assets without an intermediary clearing the settlements. Rather, peer-to-peer settlement occurs via the ledger. It also means that anyone, without authorization, can list their assets on the exchange. The procedures for listing your token on a DEX and conducting an IPO on Nasdaq are a good parallel. The latter takes one hour of work and can be completed by anyone, regardless of the token's level of establishments or duration of existence.

ETHEREUM AND DECENTRALIZED FINANCE :

With the introduction of Ethereum in 2015, two years after the publication of the whitepaper A Next-Generation Smart Contract and Decentralized Application Platform in 2013, decentralized finance (DeFi) was introduced. As previously indicated, it builds on the blockchain concept by introducing smart contracts, which enable the development of more intricate services on dispersed, decentralized networks as decentralized applications. Peer-to-peer interactions are made possible by the blockchain serving as the

settlement layer and transparent, interoperable smart contracts. This eliminates the need for intermediaries or central authorities like clearinghouses or banks. Smart contracts are self-enforcing digital agreements that are used to encode rules of conduct for any kind of interaction on the blockchain, including transactions and the establishment of new assets with specific functionalities. They can even be used to encode entire financial services, like a decentralized exchange. It is now possible to build decentralized services similar to those found in traditional finance, and to automate asset exchanges between users in a decentralized, trustless system. Similar to open-source finance, this system allows users to come and go at will and allows protocols to connect easily without authorization. One of the main advantages of DeFi is its composability, which is a byproduct of the open-source, permission less nature of cryptocurrency. Moreover, the same kind of structure can be applied to entire organizations. DAOs, or decentralized autonomous organizations, are totally controlled by the users who make up the network. This is made possible by tokens that are used to vote on proposals submitted by individuals to the network. This distributed structure has the advantage of addressing the principal-agent problem.

CHARACTERISTICS FEATURES OF DeFi :

- DeFi related projects always interact and are well integrated with each other. It is creating a very easy and a well interconnected ecosystem of all financial services.
- It encompasses a wide range of all financial services that includes trading, borrowing, lending, liquidity provision, yield farming and many more services that all are well executed in a decentralized manner through smart contracts.
- DeFi platforms can be easily accessible to everyone with a simple internet connection. It is allowing users across the globe to access all financial services without requiring any type of intermediaries or the traditional used banking infrastructures.
- All the DeFi applications are always powered by smart contracts. It is a self-executing contract with agreement’s terms that are directly written into code formats. These contracts are automated and ensure the execution of transactions without relying on any intermediaries.
- DeFi investors earn returns on their investments through common activities just like lending and liquidity provision, but they face risk that are associated with the volatility of crypto assets, then potential vulnerabilities in the smart contracts and all types of market fluctuations.

DATA ANALYSIS :

Q1. Have you heard of cryptocurrency?

Table 1.1

Opinion	Respondents	Percentage
Yes	100	100
No	0	0
Total	100	100

Table 1.2

Sample Standard Deviation, s	70.710678118655
Variance (Sample Standard), s^2	5000
Population Standard Deviation, σ	50
Variance (Population Standard), σ^2	2500
Total Numbers, N	2
Sum:	100
Mean (Average):	50
Standard Error of the Mean ($SE\bar{x}$):	50

Primary Resource:

100% of the respondents have said yes that have heard of cryptocurrency.

Q2. Do you know what is fiat currency?

Table 2.1

Opinion	Respondents	Percentage
Yes	100	100
No	0	0
Total	100	100

Table 2.2

Sample Standard Deviation, s	70.710678118655
Variance (Sample Standard), s^2	5000
Population Standard Deviation, σ	50
Variance (Population Standard), σ^2	2500
Total Numbers, N	2
Sum:	100
Mean (Average):	50
Standard Error of the Mean ($SE\bar{x}$):	50

Primary Resource:

100% of the respondents have said yes that now about fiat currency.

Q3. Do you invest in cryptocurrency?

Table 3.1

Opinion	Respondents	Percentage
Yes	70	70
No	30	30
Total	100	100

Table 3.2

Sample Standard Deviation, s	28.284271247462
Variance (Sample Standard), s^2	800
Population Standard Deviation, σ	20
Variance (Population Standard), σ^2	400
Total Numbers, N	2
Sum:	100
Mean (Average):	50
Standard Error of the Mean ($SE\bar{x}$):	20

Primary Resource:

70% of the respondents have said yes that have invested in cryptocurrency and 30% of the respondents have said no that have not invested in cryptocurrency.

Q4. Do you use any cryptocurrency wallet?

Table 4.1

Opinion	Respondents	Percentage
Yes	70	70
No	30	30
Total	100	100

Table 4.2

Sample Standard Deviation, s	28.284271247462
Variance (Sample Standard), s^2	400
Population Standard Deviation, σ	20
Variance (Population Standard), σ^2	200
Total Numbers, N	2
Sum:	100
Mean (Average):	50
Standard Error of the Mean ($SE\bar{x}$):	20

Primary Resource:

70% of the respondents have said yes that use cryptocurrency wallet and 30% of the respondents have said no that they do not use any cryptocurrency wallet.

Q5. Have you heard of DeFi based cryptocurrency tokens/coins?

Table 5.1

Opinion	Respondents	Percentage
Yes	55	55
No	45	45
Total	100	100

Table 5.2

Sample Standard Deviation, s	7.0710678118655
Variance (Sample Standard), s^2	50
Population Standard Deviation, σ	5
Variance (Population Standard), σ^2	25
Total Numbers, N	2
Sum:	100
Mean (Average):	50
Standard Error of the Mean ($SE\bar{x}$):	5

Primary Resource:

55% of the respondents have said yes that have heard of DeFi based cryptocurrency tokens/coins and 45% of the respondents have said no that have not heard of DeFi based cryptocurrency tokens/coins.

Q6. Do you invest in DeFi based cryptocurrency tokens/coins?

Table 6.1

Opinion	Respondents	Percentage
Yes	55	55
No	45	45
Total	100	100

Table 6.2

Sample Standard Deviation, s	7.0710678118655
Variance (Sample Standard), s^2	50
Population Standard Deviation, σ	5
Variance (Population Standard), σ^2	25
Total Numbers, N	2
Sum:	100
Mean (Average):	50
Standard Error of the Mean ($SE\bar{x}$):	5

Primary Resource:

55% of the respondents have said yes that they have invested in DeFi based cryptocurrency tokens/coins and 45% of the respondents have said no that they have not invested in DeFi based cryptocurrency tokens/coins.

Q7. Does your crypto wallet shows segments like Metaverse crypto tokens, DeFi crypto tokens and NFT crypto tokens?

Table 7.1

Opinion	Respondents	Percentage
Yes	70	70
No	30	30
Total	100	100

Table 7.2

Sample Standard Deviation, s	28.284271247462
Variance (Sample Standard), s^2	400
Population Standard Deviation, σ	20
Variance (Population Standard), σ^2	200
Total Numbers, N	2
Sum:	100
Mean (Average):	50
Standard Error of the Mean ($SE\bar{x}$):	20

Primary Resource:

70% of the respondents have said yes that their crypto wallet shows segments like Metaverse crypto tokens, DeFi crypto tokens and NFT crypto tokens and 30% of the respondents have said no that their crypto wallet does not shows segments like Metaverse crypto tokens, DeFi crypto tokens and NFT crypto tokens.

Q8. Have you invested in YFI, GNO, YFII, CRV any of these DeFi crypto tokens/coins?

Table 8.1

Opinion	Respondents	Percentage
Yes	55	55
No	45	45
Total	100	100

Table 8.2

Sample Standard Deviation, s	7.0710678118655
Variance (Sample Standard), s^2	50
Population Standard Deviation, σ	5
Variance (Population Standard), σ^2	25
Total Numbers, N	2
Sum:	100
Mean (Average):	50
Standard Error of the Mean ($SE\bar{x}$):	5

Primary Resource:

55% of the respondents have said yes that have invested in YFI, GNO, YFII,CRV any of these DeFi crypto tokens/coins and 45% of the respondents have said no that they have not invested in YFI, GNO,YFII,CRV any of these DeFi crypto tokens/coins.

Q9. Have you earned profit from investing in DeFi based crypto currency tokens/coins?

Table 9.1

Opinion	Respondents	Percentage
Yes	35	35
No	20	20
Not invested	45	45
Total	100	100

Table 9.2

Sample Standard Deviation, s	12.583057392118
Variance (Sample Standard), s^2	158.333333333333
Population Standard Deviation, σ	10.274023338282
Variance (Population Standard), σ^2	105.555555555556
Total Numbers, N	3
Sum:	100
Mean (Average):	33.333333333333
Standard Error of the Mean ($SE\bar{x}$):	7.2648315725678

Primary Resource:

35% of the respondents have said yes that have earned profit from investing in DeFi based crypto currency tokens/coins, 20% of the respondents have said no that they have not earned profit from investing in DeFi based crypto currency tokens/coins and 45% of the respondents have said that they have not invested in DeFi based crypto currency tokens/coins.

Q10. Does your government supports to invest in crypto currency or backs crypto assets?

Table 10.1

Opinion	Respondents	Percentage
Yes	70	70
No	30	30
Total	100	100

Table 10.2

Sample Standard Deviation, s	28.284271247462
Variance (Sample Standard), s^2	800
Population Standard Deviation, σ	20
Variance (Population Standard), σ^2	400
Total Numbers, N	2
Sum:	100
Mean (Average):	50
Standard Error of the Mean ($SE\bar{x}$):	20

Primary Resource:

70% of the respondents have said yes that their government supports to invest in crypto currency or backs crypto assets and 30% of the respondents have said no that their government supports to invest in crypto currency or backs crypto assets.

Key Findings

It was determined from this research study and the sample survey that DeFi based crypto currency tokens/coins has impacted the crypto currency market in the world. It has been noted that many investors are investing in DeFi based crypto currency tokens/coins in crypto wallet around the globe. According to the study, DeFi based crypto currency tokens/coins successfully met and kept all of its investor’s needs of the world crypto.

Advantage Investing in DeFi Crypto Currency Tokens/Coins :

- DeFi promotes inclusivity and accessibility by making its services available to anybody, wherever they may be, who has access to the internet and a digital wallet such as MetaMask. Users are not limited by customary bank processing times or related fees when executing trades and transferring assets.
- One of DeFi's main features is smart contracts, which are simple to programme and set up to act automatically depending on a variety of factors. DeFi data is more reliable because of its immutability, security, and auditability thanks to the blockchain's architectural design.
- The underlying Ethereum blockchain enables real-time transactions within DeFi. Upon completion of a transaction, the Ethereum blockchain is updated instantly. Interest rates are regularly changed, guaranteeing current and accurate data. Furthermore, all Ethereum blockchain transactions—which make up a large percentage of DeFi activities—are publicly visible and subject to peer validation. This level of openness ensures that all users are able to view network activity.

Disadvantage Investing in DeFi Crypto Currency Tokens/Coins :

- One of the most frequent dangers associated with DeFi is faulty smart contracts. Weakly coded smart contracts are an easy target for malicious actors looking to syphon off users' money.
- The majority of decentralised exchanges use liquidity pools to facilitate trading. Typically, these pools use smart contracts to lock two cryptocurrencies.

Comparison :

NFT	DeFi
NFTs always represents ownership of unique digital items.	This involves only financial activities and services.
NFT are non-fungible in nature and unique tokens	DeFi tokens are fungible in nature and can be traded interchangeably easily
It only cater to creators and collectors and mainly emphasizes on ownership of digital contents only	Focuses only on providing decentralized financial services in market
They are usually bought and sold on NFT-specific marketplaces	DeFi activities always take place on decentralized exchanges and lending platforms only.
Values of NFT are only driven by rarity, aesthetics and community demand.	DeFi token investments and ROI are mostly influenced by the performance of underlying assets and market dynamics.

Conclusion:

The study explored Ethereum and decentralized finance and all the characteristics of DeFi. The study also focused on the impact of DeFi in crypto market around the globe. The study has even highlighted advantages and disadvantages of investing in DeFi crypto currency tokens/coins. In a way never seen before, DeFi connects technical, financial, and socioeconomic complexity. Considering that DeFi was still an unusual phenomenon unrelated to the fiat system, this change could be disregarded. But as crypto assets become more and more integrated with the mainstream financial industry, we need new approaches to recognize, explore, and eventually comprehend the risks related to these advancements. The most promising solution to this challenge is the application of the scientific method within an interdisciplinary context.

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